

RISK FACTORS AND CAUSES OF SPIDER VEINS

Sometimes superficial leg veins are called spider veins. They formed due to the tiny veins congregate below the surface skin. These veins cause discoloration of red, purple, and blue color. Most of the cases of spider veins are quite small while some cases are noticeable. They are usually harmless but make you feel self-conscious. In most cases, **spider vein treatment** can be done only for cosmetic reasons.

They are also referred to as thread veins by the people. If you are tired of these small spider veins on your face then [spider vein treatment nj](#) will help you in curing and lowering the appearance.

Risk Factors of spider veins

Some of the **vein doctor near me nj** gave me these risk factors causing spider veins:

Sitting: The continuous sitting on a place for a long duration of time can also cause spider veins.

Pregnancy: During the pregnancy period, the women always suffer from spider veins.

Being overweight: Sometimes your weight can also cause you a problem like this.

Family history: If you have a family member with issues of blood clots then most probably you will suffer from this issue too.

Who's at risk?

There are millions of Americans suffering from these spider veins. The additional factors like smoking, tight clothing, and hot bath also cause spider veins.

- About 50% of women ages 40 to 55 having spider veins.
- Nearly 75% of women above 60 having spider veins
- Close to 30% of men aging 30 to 45 having spider veins.
- Around 27% of men over the age of 70 having spider veins.

Causes of spider veins

The most common area where these veins are visible is on the face, legs, and on ankles. As compared to men they are more common in women. You have to understand the causes of spider veins before going for **vein treatments**. They appear in a network that actually resembles a spider web. Mostly they are due to heredity and can be caused by the use of birth control pills.

There are other types of veins problems that can appear similar to the spider veins:

1. Angiomas and Hemangiomas are made up of very small veins called venules and small arteries called arterioles.
2. Telangiectasias are more noticeable on the face, this is dilated capillaries close to the skin.

If you are having such skin-related problems then you immediately need to seek [vein treatment near me](#).

Natural treatment for spider vein

For the treatment of spider vein treatment, you can always consult the **spider vein treatment near me**. But if you don't want to resort to medical treatment, then the best option for you is Natural remedies. Natural remedies can be a good option for you if you don't want to seek any kind of surgical treatment. It is attractive because it does not require any kind of medical prescription from any doctor. The options which are available in the natural remedies are Apple cider vinegar, Diet control, Essential oils of tea tree and lemongrass tree are such treatments.